

Corrigendum to

“A review of worldwide atmospheric mercury measurements” published in Atmos. Chem. Phys., 10, 8245–8265, 2010

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In the paper “A review of worldwide atmospheric mercury measurements” by F. Sprovieri et al. (Atmos. Chem. Phys., 10, 8245–8265, doi:10.5194/acp-10-8245-2010, 2010) references which are shown in the text are missing in the reference list. Please see the missing references below:

References

- Kim, K.-H. and Kim, M.-Y.: The temporal distribution characteristics of total gaseous mercury from an urban monitoring site in Seoul during 1999 to 2000, Atmos. Environ., 35, 4253–4263, 2001a.
- Kim, K.-H. and Kim, M.-Y.: Distribution characteristics of atmospheric mercury from two monitoring stations: inside and outside of Seoul metropolitan city, Korea, J. Korean Earth Sci. Soc., 22, 223–236, 2001b.
- Kim, M.-Y. and Kim, K.-H.: Regional distribution characteristics of total gaseous mercury in air measurements from urban and mountainous sites in Korea, Atmos. Environ., 17, 39–50, 2001c.
- Kim, K.-H., Kim, M. Y., Kim, J., and Lee, G.: Effects of changes in environmental conditions on atmospheric mercury exchange: Comparative analysis from a rice paddy field during the two spring periods of 2001 and 2002, J. Geophys. Res., 108, 4607, doi:10.1029/2003JD003375, 2003.
- Lyman, S. N. and Gustin, M. S.: Speciation of atmospheric mercury at two sites in northern Nevada, USA, Atmos. Environ., 42, 927–939, 2008.
- Nakagawa, R. and Hiromoto, M.: Geographical distribution and background levels of total mercury in air in Japan and neighboring countries, Chemosphere, 34, 801–806, 1997.
- Tan, H., He, J. L., Liang, L., Lazoff, S., Sommer, J., Xiao, Z. F., and Lindqvist, O.: Atmospheric mercury deposition in Guizhou, China, Sci. Total Environ., 259, 223–230, 2000.

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